

COMPARISON OF THE RELIABILITY OF TRANS-CEREBELLAR DIAMETER AND FETAL KIDNEY LENGTH WITH STANDARD BIOMETRIC INDICES IN ESTIMATING GESTATIONAL AGE

Dr. Spandan Seth

(JR) Department of Radio-diagnosis and Imaging
Subharti Medical College & Hospital Swami Vivekanand Subharti University,
Meerut (U.P.), India

Dr. Mukta Mita

Professor, Department of Radio-diagnosis and Imaging
Subharti Medical College & Hospital Swami Vivekanand Subharti University,
Meerut (U.P.), India

Dr. Mahesh Kumar Mittal

MD, FICR (Radiodiagnosis) Professor & Head Department of Radio-diagnosis & Imaging
Subharti Medical College & Hospital Meerut (U.P.), India

Dr. Sachin Agrawal

MD (Radiodiagnosis) Associate Professor Department of Radio-diagnosis
Subharti Medical College & Hospital Swami Vivekanand Subharti University,
Meerut (U.P.), India

Dr. Garima Khurrana

(JR) Department of Radio-diagnosis and Imaging
Subharti Medical College & Hospital Swami Vivekanand Subharti University,
Meerut (U.P.), India

ABSTRACT

Background and Aims: Accurate estimation of gestational age (GA) is critical in prenatal care, aiding in the management of pregnancies and planning interventions. Traditional methods such as last menstrual period (LMP) and standard biometric indices, including biparietal diameter (BPD), head circumference (HC), abdominal circumference (AC), and femur length (FL), show limitations in later gestation due to biological variability.

Emerging parameters such as fetal kidney length (FKL) and transverse cerebellar diameter (TCD) have shown promising reliability for GA estimation. This study compares the accuracy and reproducibility of FKL and TCD with standard biometric indices in singleton pregnancies between 28 and 34 weeks of gestation.

Methods: *This prospective observational study included 150 participants with normal singleton pregnancies, conducted at N.S.C.B. Subharti Medical College, Meerut (2023–2024). Ethical committee approval and informed consent were obtained. Ultrasonography was performed using Samsung HS70A equipment, measuring FKL, TCD, and standard indices. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 20.0.*

Results: *FKL increased linearly from 2.72 cm at 26 weeks to 3.51 cm at 35 weeks, while TCD ranged from 3.12 cm to 4.61 cm. Both showed significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) with conventional indices. FKL demonstrated minimal variability and high reproducibility, and TCD proved robust under adverse conditions like fetal growth restriction.*

Conclusion: *FKL and TCD are reliable adjuncts for GA estimation, especially when traditional parameters are inconsistent. Their integration into obstetric practice enhances accuracy and clinical decision-making.*

Keywords: Gestational Age, Fetal Kidney Length, Transverse Cerebellar Diameter, Fetal Biometry, Ultrasonography

Subject: Obstetrics and Gynecology

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INTRODUCTION

Accurate estimation of gestational age (GA) is critical for effective prenatal care and optimizing maternal and perinatal outcomes. [1] It guides crucial clinical decisions, such as scheduling labor induction, planning Cesarean deliveries, and managing high-risk pregnancies. Errors in GA assessment can lead to serious consequences, including iatrogenic prematurity or post-maturity, both of which are associated with increased perinatal morbidity and mortality. [2,3] Traditional methods for GA determination, such as relying on the last menstrual period (LMP) or physical examination, often fall short in accuracy, particularly in cases of irregular menstrual cycles, uncertain LMP dates, or early pregnancy bleeding. [4,5] In such scenarios, ultrasonography has become the gold standard for GA assessment due to its reliability, non-invasiveness, and reproducibility. [6]

Currently, standard ultrasonographic parameters used for fetal biometry include bi-parietal diameter (BPD), head circumference (HC), abdominal circumference (AC), and femur length (FL). These measurements provide reliable GA estimation in the early stages of pregnancy. [7,8] However, their accuracy diminishes as gestation advances due to biological variability in fetal size. Moreover, conditions like altered skull shape, skeletal anomalies, intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), or multiple pregnancies can significantly affect these measurements, making them less dependable in the second and third trimesters. [9,10]

To overcome these limitations, newer parameters such as fetal kidney length (FKL) and trans-cerebellar diameter (TCD) have been introduced as alternative markers for GA estimation. FKL is a robust parameter, showing a consistent growth rate throughout pregnancy, unaffected by growth disorders or anomalies. [11,12] This makes it especially useful in cases of growth-restricted fetuses or when traditional measurements are unreliable. Similarly, TCD, which represents the transverse diameter of the cerebellum, has emerged as another reliable marker. The cerebellum is protected from external pressures and demonstrates a linear growth pattern, correlating strongly with GA. Unlike other indices, TCD remains unaffected by conditions like fetal growth restriction, brachycephaly, or dolichocephaly, making it a dependable indicator, especially in late gestation. [12,13]

This study aims to compare the reliability of FKL and TCD with standard biometric indices for GA estimation in normal singleton pregnancies between 28 and 34 weeks of gestation. By evaluating the accuracy and reproducibility of these emerging parameters, this research seeks to provide valuable insights into their potential role in enhancing prenatal care and addressing the challenges posed by traditional methods, particularly in complex pregnancies.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This prospective observational study was conducted in the Department of Radiodiagnosis, Imaging & Interventional Radiology, N.S.C.B. Subharti Medical College, C.S.S. Hospital, Meerut, under Swami Vivekanand Subharti University. The study duration was from February 2023 to June 2024. A total of 170 patients were enrolled, out of which 20 were excluded based on the predefined criteria, resulting in 150 participants included for final analysis.

The inclusion criteria comprised normal singleton pregnancies between 28 and 34 weeks of gestation confirmed by a known last menstrual period (LMP) or a documented dating scan, and maternal age between 20 and 45 years. Exclusion criteria included discrepancies of two or more weeks between gestational age calculated by LMP and ultrasound (AUA), multiple pregnancies, fetal anomalies, chromosomal abnormalities, and cases of intrauterine fetal death (IUFD). Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee, and written informed consent was secured from all participants. Additionally, PC-PNDT Form F was completed for every subject.

Ultrasound scans were conducted using a Samsung HS70A ultrasound machine with a 3.5–5 MHz curvilinear transducer, performed by the same operator to ensure consistency. The parameters measured included trans-cerebellar diameter (TCD), fetal kidney length (FKL), biparietal diameter (BPD), head circumference (HC), abdominal circumference (AC), femur length (FL), fetal heart rate (FHR), estimated fetal weight, amniotic fluid index (AFI), and placental position.

TCD was measured by obtaining the cerebellar view in the posterior cranial fossa, visualizing the hemispheres and cisterna magna, and measuring the widest transverse diameter of the cerebellum. FKL was measured in the sagittal plane by capturing the entire length of a single kidney from upper to lower poles, taking three measurements, and recording the mean. BPD and HC were measured transaxially at the level of the paired thalami and cavum septum pellucidi, with HC traced using the ellipse method. AC was measured transversely at the level of the stomach and intrahepatic umbilical vein. FL was determined by aligning the transducer along the diaphysis, excluding cartilaginous epiphyses. FHR was recorded using M-mode by measuring peak-to-peak waveforms.

Data were entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS Version 20.0 software. Appropriate statistical methods were applied depending on the type and distribution of data. Results were expressed in tables and graphs for clarity and comprehensive analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1 represents the mean values of Fetal Kidney Length (FKL) and Trans-Cerebellar Diameter (TCD) along with their respective ranges and standard deviations. FKL had a mean of 3.17 cm, while TCD had a mean of 3.88 cm, reflecting their reliability as gestational markers.

Parameter	Minimum (cm)	Maximum (cm)	Mean (cm)	Std. Deviation
FKL (cm)	2.72	3.52	3.17	0.18
TCD (cm)	3.12	4.66	3.88	0.32

Graph 1: Mean FKL and TCD

Table 2 represents the mean Fetal Kidney Length (FKL) and Trans-Cerebellar Diameter (TCD) from 28 to 34 weeks of gestation. The measurements show a steady linear increase with advancing gestational age. FKL values range from 2.84 cm at 28 weeks to 3.33 cm at 34 weeks, with narrow confidence intervals indicating consistency. Similarly, TCD values increase from 3.33 cm at 28 weeks to 4.15 cm at 34 weeks, demonstrating reliability as a gestational marker.

GA Weeks	Mean FKL (cm)	Std. Deviation (FKL)	95% CI		Mean TCD (cm)	Std. Deviation (TCD)	95% CI	
			Lower (FKL)	Upper (FKL)			Lower (TCD)	Upper (TCD)
28 wk	2.84	0.07	2.80	2.87	3.33	0.12	3.26	3.40
29 wk	2.98	0.10	2.93	3.03	3.57	0.11	3.50	3.62
30 wk	3.01	0.11	2.95	3.08	3.58	0.20	3.47	3.69
31 wk	3.18	0.10	3.13	3.24	3.84	0.15	3.76	3.92
32 wk	3.27	0.12	3.20	3.34	4.05	0.23	3.92	4.18
33 wk	3.33	0.09	3.29	3.38	4.13	0.15	4.04	4.22
34 wk	3.33	0.11	3.27	3.40	4.15	0.25	4.01	4.30

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Graph 2: Mean FKL and TCD with 95% CI

Table 3 represents the mean Fetal Kidney Length (FKL) and Trans-Cerebellar Diameter (TCD) across gestational ages (AUA) weeks, along with their standard deviations and 95% confidence intervals. The steady linear increase in both parameters underscores their reliability as gestational markers. FKL shows minimal variability with a peak of 3.51 cm at 35 weeks, while TCD reaches 4.61 cm with similar consistency.

GA (AUA) Weeks	Mean FKL (cm)	Std. Deviation (FKL)	95% CI		Mean TCD (cm)	Std. Deviation (TCD)	95% CI	
			Lower (FKL)	Upper (FKL)			Lower (TCD)	Upper (TCD)
26 wk	2.72	—	2.76	2.83	3.12	—	3.12	3.32
27 wk	2.80	0.02	2.82	2.89	3.22	0.04	3.32	3.39
28 wk	2.85	0.06	2.92	3.02	3.35	0.06	3.49	3.57
29 wk	2.97	0.07	3.05	3.09	3.53	0.06	3.66	3.70
30 wk	3.07	0.04	3.13	3.17	3.68	0.05	3.81	3.85
31 wk	3.15	0.05	3.22	3.25	3.83	0.05	4.01	4.07
32 wk	3.23	0.05	3.34	3.38	4.04	0.08	4.12	4.23
33 wk	3.36	0.04	3.43	3.49	4.17	0.13	4.38	4.45
34 wk	3.46	0.05	4.45	4.77	4.41	0.05	—	—
35 wk	3.51	0.01	—	—	4.61	0.06	—	—

Graph 3: Mean FKL and TCD with SD across GA (AUA) weeks

Table 4 represents the correlation of gestational age (GA) with standard biometric indices (BPD, HC, AC, FL) and emerging markers (FKL, TCD) based on both LMP and AUA models. Significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) were observed for FL, FKL, and TCD in both models, highlighting their reliability in GA estimation. The data emphasizes the utility of TCD and FKL as robust alternatives to standard parameters, especially in uncertain cases.

Parameter	LMP						AUA							
	Coefficient	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	p-value	95% CI		Coefficient	Std. Error	Beta	t-value	p-value	95% CI	
						Lower	Upper						Lower	Upper
BPD	0.226	0.482	0.061	0.470	0.639	-0.727	1.180	1.098	0.155	0.278	7.096	0.0001	0.792	1.403
HC	0.050	0.148	0.044	0.338	0.736	-0.243	0.344	0.138	0.048	0.114	2.889	0.004	0.043	0.232
AC	0.099	0.099	0.111	1.001	0.318	-0.096	0.293	0.179	0.032	0.191	5.651	0.0001	0.116	0.241
FL	2.994	0.574	0.729	5.214	0.001	1.859	4.130	0.975	0.184	0.224	5.292	0.0001	0.611	1.339
FKL	1.837	1.886	0.193	0.974	0.032	-1.891	5.566	-0.607	0.605	-	-1.003	0.017	-1.803	0.589
TCD	-1.391	1.018	-	-1.367	0.017	-3.403	0.621	1.631	0.326	0.286	4.994	0.0001	0.985	2.276

Table 5 represents the linear regression analysis of Fetal Kidney Length (FKL) and Trans-Cerebellar Diameter (TCD) with standard biometric parameters (BPD, HC, AC, FL). Both FKL and TCD show significant correlations ($p < 0.05$) with all parameters, underscoring their reliability as additional markers for gestational assessment.

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Parameter	FKL						TCD					
	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-value	p-value	95% CI		Coefficient	Std. Error	t-value	p-value	95% CI	
					Lower	Upper					Lower	Upper
BPD	0.119	0.019	6.332	0.000	0.082	0.157	0.067	0.035	1.914	0.050	-0.002	0.136
HC	0.020	0.006	3.377	0.001	0.008	0.031	0.061	0.011	5.688	0.001	0.040	0.083
AC	0.022	0.004	5.874	0.0001	0.015	0.029	0.035	0.007	5.136	0.001	0.022	0.049
FL	0.141	0.018	7.636	0.0002	0.104	0.177	0.321	0.034	9.411	0.011	0.254	0.389

Graph No 4: Scatter diagram showing the correlation and regression analysis of the transcerebellar diameter (cm) with gestational age.

Graph no. 5: Scatter diagram showing the correlation and regression analysis of the fetal kidney length (cm) with gestational age

Graph no. 6: Scatter diagram showing the correlation and regression analysis of the BPD (cm) with gestational age

Graph no. 7: Scatter diagram showing the correlation and regression analysis of the HC (cm) with gestational age

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Graph no. 8: Scatter diagram showing the correlation and regression analysis of the AC (cm) with gestational age

Graph no. 9: Scatter diagram showing the correlation and regression analysis of the FL (cm) with gestational age

ILLUSTRATIVE IMAGES

Fig 1: Biparietal diameter (BPD) measurements for a patient of 30 weeks 2 days period of gestational age by USG (AUA). BPD measured ~ 7.6 cm, corresponding to 30 weeks 3 days.

Fig 2: Biparietal diameter (BPD) measurements for a patient of 33 weeks 2 days period of gestational age by USG (AUA). BPD measured ~ 8.3 cm, corresponding to 33 weeks 4 days.

Comparison of the Reliability of Trans-Cerebellar Diameter and Fetal Kidney Length with Standard Biometric Indices in Estimating Gestational Age

Fig 3: Head circumference (HC) measurements for a patient of 31 weeks 2 days period of gestational age by USG (AUA). HC measured ~ 7.6 cm, corresponding to 31 weeks 1 days.

Fig 4: Head circumference (HC) measurements for a patient of 33 weeks 2 days period of gestational age by USG (AUA). HC measured ~ 29.2 cm, corresponding to 33 weeks 4 days

Fig 5: Abdominal circumference (AC) measurements for a patient of 31 weeks 4 days period of gestational age by USG (AUA). AC measured ~ 27.0 cm, corresponding to 31 weeks 1 days.

Fig 6: Abdominal circumference (AC) measurements for a patient of 33 weeks 2 days period of gestational age by USG (AUA). AC measured ~ 29.1 cm, corresponding to 33 weeks 0 days.

Comparison of the Reliability of Trans-Cerebellar Diameter and Fetal Kidney Length with Standard Biometric Indices in Estimating Gestational Age

Fig 7: Femur length (FL) measurements for a patient of 33 weeks 2 days period of gestational age by USG (AUA). FL measured ~ 29.1 cm, corresponding to 33 weeks 0 days.

Fig 8: Femur length (FL) measurements for a patient of 32 weeks 2 days period of gestational age by USG (AUA). FL measured ~ 6.4 cm, corresponding to 33 weeks 0 days.

Fig 9: A & B, showing measurements of trans-cerebellar diameter (TCD) at various ages of gestation. A:3.85 cm for 31w5d GA(AUA) and B :4.11 cm for 33w0d GA(AUA) respectively.

Fig 10: A & B showing measurements of fetal kidney length (FKL) at various ages of gestation. A: 3.20 cm for 31w5d GA(AUA) and B : 3.36 cm for 33w0d GA(AUA) respectively.

Fig 11: Antenatal USG of a patient with GA by sonography (AUA) corresponding to 33 week 2 days. On (A) shows moderately dilated pelvicalyceal system of both kidneys. On (B) shows urinary bladder which was distended & elongated with a keyhole appearance. Above findings suggested possibility of posterior urethral valve. On postnatal scan, findings of the same were confirmed. However, this patient was excluded from the study.

DISCUSSION

Accurate estimation of gestational age (GA) is essential for effective prenatal care, particularly for determining fetal maturity, planning delivery, and managing complications. Traditional methods, such as calculating GA based on the last menstrual period (LMP), have limitations, especially when the LMP is uncertain or irregular. Ultrasound-based fetal biometry offers a reliable alternative, using parameters like biparietal diameter (BPD), head circumference (HC), abdominal circumference (AC), and femur length (FL). However, as gestation progresses, biological variations affect the accuracy of these parameters. This study explores the utility of fetal kidney length (FKL) and transverse cerebellar diameter (TCD) as adjunctive markers for GA estimation, comparing them with standard biometric indices.

The findings of this study align with existing literature, demonstrating the reliability of FKL and TCD as supplementary parameters for GA estimation. FKL increased linearly with gestational age, ranging from 2.72 cm at 26 weeks to 3.51 cm at 35 weeks (AUA), with a strong correlation ($p < 0.05$) to conventional biometric indices. This is consistent with the work of *Singh A et al. [1]* similarly reported FKL values of 2.15 ± 0.01 cm at 19 weeks and 3.87 ± 0.19 cm at 39 weeks. These results highlight the stability of FKL across varying conditions, making it particularly valuable in cases of growth disorders or when conventional parameters are less reliable.

TCD also showed a significant linear relationship with gestational age, increasing from 3.12 cm at 26 weeks to 4.61 cm at 35 weeks (AUA). The strong correlation ($p < 0.05$) between TCD and GA underscores its value as a reliable marker. Previous studies by *Singh A et al. [1]* and *Bansal M et al. [14]* support these findings, noting a significant positive correlation between TCD and GA throughout pregnancy. *Chavez MR et al. [15]* and *Scott JA et al. [16]* further highlighted TCD's robustness as it remains unaffected by external factors like fetal distress, emphasizing its reliability even in adverse conditions.

The comparison of GA derived from LMP and AUA revealed that both FKL and TCD correlated well with all conventional parameters. FKL was particularly advantageous in scenarios involving small AC or engaged fetal heads, where standard indices like HC or BPD may be challenging to measure accurately. The study also found a strong correlation between GA and FL, BPD, HC, and AC, consistent with the findings of *Ugur MG et al. [17]* and *Walad R et al. [18]*. This reinforces the reliability of conventional parameters, while highlighting the additional value of FKL and TCD in cases where these indices may fall short.

The correlation of FKL with BPD, HC, AC, and FL was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$), suggesting that FKL complements these conventional parameters effectively. Similar findings were reported by *Dahmarde H et al. [2]*, who observed a positive association of FKL with HC, AC, BPD, and FL. The steady growth of fetal kidneys, unaffected by external factors, makes FKL a dependable marker, as noted by *Witzani L et al. [10]* and *Kaul I et al. [19]*, who reported a consistent increase of approximately 1.7 mm every 14 days during pregnancy. The clinical utility of FKL is further supported by *Ahmadi et al. [20]*, who recommended its use in dating labor when LMP data is unavailable or unreliable.

TCD also demonstrated strong correlations with conventional parameters like BPD, HC, AC, and FL. The study by *Singh A et al. [1]* showed that TCD had the best correlation with HC and the least with AC, a trend observed in this study as well. The work of *Swaminathan M et al.* and *Bansal M et al. [14]* highlighted TCD's unique role in gestational dating, noting its consistent growth pattern throughout pregnancy. This makes TCD a valuable alternative when other parameters are difficult to measure, such as in cases of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) or abnormal fetal positioning.

In conclusion, the study highlights the complementary role of FKL and TCD in improving the accuracy of GA estimation. Both parameters show strong correlations with conventional biometric indices, supporting their integration into routine obstetric practice. These findings align with existing research, emphasizing the value of FKL and TCD in situations where traditional measurements may be less reliable. Future studies should explore the optimal combination of biometric parameters to achieve even greater accuracy in gestational dating, particularly in complex clinical scenarios.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Future studies should evaluate the accuracy of FKL and TCD in high-risk pregnancies, including cases of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) and fetal anomalies. Incorporating larger sample sizes and longitudinal follow-ups across diverse populations would enhance the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, exploring the integration of FKL and TCD with advanced imaging technologies could further improve gestational age estimation.

LIMITATIONS

The study was limited to normal singleton pregnancies between 28 and 34 weeks of gestation, excluding high-risk cases like multiple pregnancies and fetal anomalies. A single-center design may limit the applicability of results to broader populations. Operator dependency in ultrasonographic measurements could introduce variability in parameter accuracy.

CONCLUSION

We concluded that fetal kidney length (FKL) and transverse cerebellar diameter (TCD) are reliable markers for estimating gestational age (GA), demonstrating significant correlations with conventional biometric indices such as BPD, HC, AC, and FL. FKL showed minimal variability and consistent growth across gestational weeks, while TCD exhibited linear increases with advancing GA, underscoring their accuracy and reproducibility.

These parameters are particularly useful in cases of uncertain LMP or when traditional indices are challenging to measure, offering robust alternatives for precise gestational assessment.

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Ethical Approval: Ethical approval was obtained and documented as per institutional guidelines.

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